

**INFORMATIONAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL INFLUENCE
IN THE CONTEXT OF THE RUSSIAN-UKRAINIAN HYBRID WAR:
ANALYSIS AND IMPACT ON SOCIETY**

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Informational and psychological influence in modern conflicts is gaining more and more relevance and significance. The Russian-Ukrainian hybrid war became an example of the use of informational and psychological methods and ways of waging war with a new generation.

The purpose of this work is to conduct an analysis of informational and psychological influence in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian hybrid war and to consider the strategies and consequences of such influence on society.

The Russian Federation has widely used information and psychological influence as an effective tool in modern hybrid warfare against Ukraine for many years. The population of Ukraine is under constant informational and psychological pressure from the aggressor country. The full-scale military aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine on February 24, 2022, as another stage of the Russian-Ukrainian war, shocked the world and undermined the entire basis of the international order that existed after the end of the Cold War and the collapse of the USSR. Although the plans of this attack were known to the intelligence of the West and Ukraine and its threat was very well covered by the Western media this war is the first large-scale war in Europe since the end of the Second World War [1, 2].

The Russian Federation has been preparing for a hybrid war against Ukraine for a long time. These processes became more active when V. Putin came to power. The next strategic plans for the so-called "liberation of Ukraine" were successfully developed and put into practice in the Russian Federation immediately after the Orange Revolution (in 2005), when V. Yanukovich failed to be brought to power. These plans were both relatively "peaceful", using "soft power", and "forceful", using means of lethal damage.

The so-called "peace plans" of the Russian Federation were based on a controlled pro-Russian government in Ukraine, fully controlled internal and external processes, total censorship, and control in the information space. The strategic goal was also the collapse of the Ukrainian defense and security sector, the holding of referendums on the "voluntary" return of Crimea to "its native harbor" (joining the Russian Federation), the rewriting of the Ukrainian Constitution following Russian standards, the federalization of Ukraine, the destruction of Ukrainian identity through complete infection with the virus of the "Russian world", and as a result - the destruction of Ukraine as an independent country.

In the future, preparation for the next hybrid actions, including actions from the territory of Ukraine to other countries of the European Union was foreseen. First of all, those countries that left the Soviet space after the collapse of the USSR. Such a fate befell modern Belarus, which passed through "soft power" and was practically absorbed by the Russian Federation, from whose territory the Russian army entered Ukraine in February 2022 and committed genocide of the Ukrainian population [3, 4].

Regarding the "forceful" options for the development of events in the process of the so-called "liberation of Ukraine", which complement the previous "peaceful" plans of V. Putin, in addition, several forceful actions are added, as a result of which a hybrid of kinetic and non-kinetic actions aimed at restoring the "Great Russian Empire".

In particular, this is the " Doctrine of Gerasimov" (2013) and the subsequent actions of the Russian Federation regarding Ukraine in the period 2014-2022, which

fully coincide with the theses of this doctrine [5]. "Doctrine of Gerasimov 2.0" (2019), which was introduced already after the annexation of Crimea, the invasion of eastern Ukraine, and hostilities involving the Russian Federation in Syria. This "Doctrine" already defines the transition from the so-called "internal conflict" provoked by the Russian Federation in Ukraine to the preparation of the Russian Federation for a full-scale war and large-scale occupation of Ukraine, the so-called "special military operation" [6].

It is also worth paying attention to the strategy called "Operation Mechanical Orange", which gained publicity in 2008 in the media. Initially, it was published as an analytical article on the pages of the propaganda site "Russian Magazine" and actively spread on the Internet [7]. At that time, the majority of the population of Ukraine did not believe in such insidious plans of the "brotherly nation" described in the material of the article. Since 2014 (after the Revolution of Dignity and the escape of V. Yanukovich from Ukraine, *the president of Ukraine at that time*), the Russian Federation has started implementing them against Ukraine with almost 100% analogy.

In 2008, watching the events in the Caucasus during the Russian-Georgian war, many people simply did not realize that Ukraine would be next after Georgia. Georgia, unlike Belarus, did resist the Russian Federation and, although it temporarily lost territories, nevertheless kept its independence [8].

For a long time, the Russian Federation covertly dominated the Ukrainian information space, and systematically carried out informational and psychological influence on the population of Ukraine, both before 2014 and at the beginning of the Anti-terrorist operation in the east of Ukraine in 2014. Ukrainian information space was not protected for a long time, and the society was not ready for such a large amount of disinformation and systematic informational and psychological influence that was carried out by the Russian Federation.

The information front of the modern hybrid war of the Russian Federation against Ukraine mainly focuses on the following objects of influence (target audience): the population of Ukraine in the conflict zone; the population of

temporarily occupied territories; the population of the territory of Ukraine, which is not covered by the conflict; own population (citizens of the Russian Federation); international community. Considering informational and psychological influence as a threat, it is necessary to understand the negative consequences of its implementation. Such consequences can be manifested in the views and actions of the person on whom this influence is exerted (the object of influence), towards the surrounding world, in the destruction of the integrity of his personality and, as a result, some reactions, namely his actions or inaction, which is the goal of this influence.

As a result of the successful implementation of such measures by the Russian Federation (subject of influence) – social ideas, views, ideas, beliefs, negative emotions, and feelings, motives of mistrust and dissatisfaction with the actions of the country's leadership are formed or supported in the mind of the subject of influence (target audience). The Russian Federation uses various sources of information (channels of information delivery) to implement informational and psychological influence for the target audience. In particular, in the physical space, it is sound broadcasting, the spread of printed and oral propaganda, and in the digital space, it is the Internet network, television and radio broadcasting, etc. [9].

The majority of the population of Ukraine has access to the Internet, which is why the Internet was and remains one of the most effective channels actively used by Russia to deliver information to the object of influence in various ways during the Russian-Ukrainian war. Enemy Internet resources, which, as a rule, are disguised as Ukrainian and foreign resources, are the sites of news agencies, periodicals, blogs, forums, thematic pages, and groups in social networks, which are created and supported with the main purpose – to influence the consciousness of the object of influence. These resources, with attractive headlines, encourage reading the information contained in the messages and influence the feelings and emotions of readers with the help of provocative, false, or manipulative information. Also, in the course of the Russian Federation's implementation of informational and psychological influence against Ukraine, internet trolls and targeted advertising became widely used.

As a rule, Internet trolls operate on social networks and impersonate themselves as ordinary Ukrainian users. The main task of such virtual users is to distribute influence materials, find and attract a potential target audience to actively participate in discussions, encourage them to join thematic groups, and encourage them to view the necessary content with the sole ultimate goal – changing the behavior of the target audience in favor of the enemy [10].

Targeted advertising, as in business, is a way of using methods and settings to find the target audience according to given parameters (social profile, interests, needs, location, etc.). As a rule, it is used by Russia in social networks to popularize the channels of information delivery among the target audience and to exert influence [11].

The main ways and methods of the Russian Federation's informational and psychological influence with the use of Internet trolls and targeted advertising remain: spreading disinformation; undermining morale and psychological pressure; propaganda and discrediting; cultural influence, etc. The implementation of cyber-attacks on critical infrastructure, and the use of special software complexes and artificial intelligence are becoming an integral part of the Russian Federation hybrid war against Ukraine, which brings new challenges and threats to society and the state as a whole.

Ukrainian society is faced with a difficult task in the conditions of the Russian Federation hybrid war, which uses a variety of methods of informational and psychological influence to achieve its political and strategic goals. Analyzing this impact, several conclusions can be drawn that may be useful for developing countermeasures and protection strategies for society.

First, it is important to determine that informational and psychological influence is becoming more and more influential in modern wars and requires a comprehensive approach to combating it. It is necessary to focus our efforts on increasing media literacy among the population, strengthening internal information security mechanisms, and promoting the development of independent media.

Secondly, the information war has a significant impact on the psychological state of society, in particular on the formation of public opinion, interpretation of events, and attitude to political processes. In this regard, it is necessary to intensify the activities of public organizations, psychological support, and programs to counter propaganda and manipulation by the Russian Federation.

After all, it is important to preserve the unity of society and maintain the trust of citizens in their own country, preventing destabilization and disinformation. For this, it is necessary to maintain a dialogue between different social groups, provide open access to information, and promote active citizen participation in decisions concerning the future of the country.

In general, the analysis of the informational and psychological impact in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian hybrid war indicates the need for constant improvement of countermeasures and protection of society against this type of aggression. Only through the joint efforts of the government, the public, and the international community can the stability and independence of society be ensured in the conditions of hybrid warfare.

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